

REUSE OF WASTE CARBON FIBRE BY COMPOUNDING WITH THERMOPLASTIC POLYMERS

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SUMMARY

Composites of Polypropylene and Polyethylene with three types of continuous sized carbon fibres were manufactured using twin screw compounding. The carbon fibres used were collected as waste product form the 3D weaving process. Compounds with various percentages of reinforcement were injection moulded and tested for mechanical properties.

Keywords: Thermoplastic composites, Waste, Compounding, Carbon fibre, polymer

ABSTRACT

Composites of Polypropylene (PP) and High Density Polyethylene (HDPE) with three types of continuous sized waste carbon fibres (CF) were manufactured using twin screw compounding. The carbon fibres used were collected as waste product form the 3D weaving process. Compounds with various percentages, between 4.6 % and 15.5 % fibre volume fraction, of reinforcement were injection moulded. Tensile testing was carried out to access the change in Young's modulus, tensile strength and elongation at break. Also, micrographic analysis was conducted to observe the importance of sizing and the effect of its removal. It was determined that the Young's modulus and tensile strength of the composite increased with increasing carbon fibre loading, whereas the elongation at break was reduced. Also, it was determined that an increase in tensile strength could be obtained by removal of the epoxy size.

INTRODUCTION

With the desire to produce composites materials which are less susceptible to delamination by transverse impact loading, 3D weaving [1] is becoming a viable method for the manufacture of preforms for aerospace applications. As with any process, 3D weaving (and other textile processes) produces some superfluous material in the form of waste product. In the case of 3D weaving, the waste product is high value carbon fibre yarn, rewound on short spool ends, which are removed form the process when the bobbins on the creel are replaced during restring or scheduled maintenance. Bobbins can also be removed from the creel if they have become damaged by entanglement or frictional effects or if the sizing is out of life. As a result, the weaver is forced to dispose of these short ends by dumping in land fill. If 3D weaving is to evolve into a fully economic, environmentally sustainable

method for creation of next generation aero structures, some form of reuse of the waste carbon fibre stream must be explored. Today, most carbon fibre still finds its way into aerospace applications, such as the new A350, 787 Dreamliner or C-Series, but carbon fibre use is increasing in industrial applications also. There has been a move towards the use of liquid moulding technology which generally requires the use of a woven or stitched form of dry fabric rather than the more traditional methods of pre-impregnation of unidirectional tape.

The increased production of carbon/ epoxy composites in recent years has greatly increased the amount of waste materials [2]. Traditional methods have concentrated largely on disposal in landfill sites. Because of decreasing landfill space and increasing landfill costs, other approaches need to be developed for recycling and reuse. Carbon fibre in the dry form provides a strong, stiff and low density reinforcement. Recovered waste carbon fibre from the weaving process can be used to reinforce thermoplastics or thermosets to improve their physical and mechanical properties [3]. The use of carbon fibres in the production of polymer composites for high-technology applications is increasing rapidly because of their good mechanical, thermal and electrical properties [4].

In general, a high fibre content is required in order to achieve a high performance short fibre reinforced composite. Therefore, the effect of fibre content on the mechanical properties of short fibre reinforced composites is of particular interest and significance. It is often observed that the increase in fibre content leads to the increase in the strength and modulus [5]. In this article we report the production of recovered waste carbon fibre composites by melt compounding and injection moulding. For comparative purposes, composites having been produced using two different thermoplastic matrices (polypropylene, PP, and polyethylene, HDPE) which are part of the group of commodity thermoplastics produced in large quantities. The percentage loading of carbon fibre is examined and correlated with tensile mechanical results. Furthermore, the effect of removal of the epoxy specific chemical sizing is examined.

EXPERIMENTAL

The waste carbon fibre used in the study was removed from the creel of a DATAWEAVE loom with Jacquard controller incorporating 1152 bobbins, at the end of a weaving production run. The composites were prepared by feeding the carbon fibre (CF) roving from the short bobbin ends into the polymer melt using a 16mm twin-screw extruder with an L:D ratio of 15:1 (ThermoScientific, Haake Rheomex OS PTW16). Two types of thermoplastic polymer were investigated. A High density Polyethylene with a MFI of 8.5 g/10min and a PP impact copolymer with an MFI of 7g/10min. The continuous CF was directly fed into the extruder by the rotation of the screws. 3K, 6K and 12K CF was used to compound the sample material. 3K, 6K and 12K are abbreviations for CF containing 3000, 6000 and 12000 filaments in one yarn of CF. Hence the loading factor is determined by the CF used, as polymer feed rate and screw speed are kept constant. In Table 1 the filament yarn data is presented. Table 2 shows the parameters used for extrusion. The fibres were fed through a window located after the first mixing section, after melting of the polymer, in

order to minimize fibre degradation, since it is known that this occurs mainly at the transition from the solid to the molten state [6]. The six heating zones were set to the process temperature (Table 2) and the compounded extrudates were immediately quenched in water bath at 20°C and cooled in air to ambient temperature. Then the extruded strands were chopped into granules of an average length of 3.1mm and diameter of 2.47mm.

Table 1. Material supplier data for filament yarn.

Fibre type	Sizing base	Tensile strength/ MPa	Tensile modulus/ GPa
12K HTS	polyurethane	4300	240
6K HTA	epoxy resin	3950	238
3K HTA	epoxy resin	3950	238

Table 2. Process parameters for extrusion.

Material	Temperature °C	Feed rate %	rpm min
HDPE	200	10	160
PP	220	10	160

Tensile test specimens were then injection moulded using a ThermoScientific Haake miniJet II. The tensile specimens were moulded to shape according to ASTM D638 [7]. The parameters for the injection moulding are shown in table 3. Five tensile specimens from each combination of polymer and CF were tensile tested on a Zwick Z100 universal tester. An MTS 632.85F biaxial extensometer was used to determine tensile modulus. All the samples were tested at a speed of 1mm/min. The results of these tests were compared with non compound (polymer material with no CF denoted as Pure HDPE and Pure PP) material as the baseline values. The fracture surfaces of all material types were investigated with a stereo microscope.

In an attempt to determine the effect of the epoxy specific sizing (Table 1). The 6k fibre was chosen for removal of sizing and comparison of results. This was implemented by the emersion of a length of 6k fibre in acetone for a period of 24 hours. The samples with sized removed are denoted as unsized (US).

Table 3. Injection moulding parameters.

Material	Cylinder temp. °C	Mould temp. °C	Pressure bar	Pressure time s	Post pressure bar	Post pressure time s
HDPE	190	60	500	7	300	5
PP	220	60	500	7	300	5

Thermogravimetric Analysis (TGA) was used to determine the fibre volume fraction. This was carried out using a 951 Thermogravimetric Analyzer by TA instruments. For each sample, approximately 6 mg of composite material was heated from room temperature at 10°C/min, up to a temperature of 600°C at a ramp rate of 10°C/min in a nitrogen environment. The weight loss of resin was calculated giving a value for fibre weight fraction which could be converted to volume fraction. An initial run over the temperature range was conducted on carbon fibre to confirm that all the weight loss could be attributed to polymer degradation.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 1 shows the tensile Young's modulus for materials tested. It is clear that for both polymer types a large increase in modulus can be obtained by the addition of waste carbon fibre (CF) which has been recovered from the 3D weaving process. The HDPE with no CF (Pure HDPE) had a modulus of 1.21 GPa and the PP with no CF (Pure PP) had a modulus of 1.33 GPa. With the addition of the 3k CF we see a 194% increase in the modulus to 3.56 GPa. The addition of 6k fibre to the HDPE provides a 432% increase in modulus to 6.44 GPa and the addition of 12k CF provides a 1004% increase in modulus to 13.3 GPa. Similarly, the addition of 3k CF with PP produces a 152% increase in modulus bringing the value to 3.36 GPa. The addition of 6k CF with PP provided a 389% increase to 6.51 GPa and the addition of 12k gave a 956% increase to 14.1 GPa. It was found that the removal of sizing from the 6k CF creates a slight reduction in modulus when compared to sized fibres for both polymer types. The PE specimen with unsized 6k (HDPE 6k US) gave a modulus of 5.5 GPa representing a 14.1% reduction compared with sized PE with 6k CF. The PP specimen with unsized 6k (PP 6k US) gave a modulus of 6.48 GPa representing less than 0.5% reduction compared with sized PP with 6k CF.

Figure 1. Young's modulus for materials tested.

Figure 2. Ultimate tensile Strength for materials tested.

The values for ultimate tensile strength (UTS) (Figure 2) generally displayed a similar trend to the modulus values. It was found that the addition of recovered CF can significantly improve the ultimate tensile strength by up to 77% in the case of HDPE with 12k CF. With this polymer type, lower CF loading levels were also found to impart beneficial properties to the composite. The addition of 3k CF give an 11% increase in UTS whereas the addition of 6k CF give a 38% improvement. The improvements for the PP composite were not as marked with the addition of 3K CF actually degrading the UTS properties. However, as the CF loading was increased by the addition of 6K CF an improvement of 10% was observed as compared to the base properties of the polymer (Pure PP). The addition of 12k brings this value to 25% improvement. The results for the unsized CF were very different for both polymer types. The PE specimen with unsized 6k (HDPE 6k US) gave a UTS of 44MPa representing a 58% increase compared with sized PE with 6k CF. The PP specimen with unsized 6k (PP 6k US) gave a UTS of 24 MPa representing an 18% reduction compared with sized PP with 6k CF.

Figure 3 shows the values for elongation at break. The values for elongation at break for the pure HDPE and PP exhibited similar values with pure HDPE giving a 135% elongation at break and pure PP giving a 140% elongation at break. It is clear from the results that although a significant increase in modulus and ultimate tensile strength can be obtained by addition of CF, the % elongation at break is vastly reduced. The addition of 3k CF reduces the values to 34% and 42% for HDPE and PP respectively representing a 74% and 70% reduction in elongation at break. This trend is continued with the addition of 6k CF; the addition of 12k CF further reduced the values to 0.7% and 0.6% for HDPE and PP respectively, representing a 99.5% reduction in elongation at break for both materials. It was found that the removal of the sizing on the 6k CF gave an increase in elongation at break. For the HDPE 6k US sample, the removal of sizing increased the value of elongation

at break from 3% to 3.9%, representing a 30% increase. The increase obtained for PP by the removal of the sizing was more marked with an increase in elongation at break from 4% to 7% representing a 75% increase.

Figure 3. Elongation at break for materials tested.

It is generally thought that under tensile loading, the cracks start at the fibre ends and propagate along the fibre–matrix interface or cross through the matrix before failure. Fibre ends have been shown to substantially concentrate the stress in the adjacent matrix [8], producing stress magnifications. The effects of these stress concentrations can be relieved only by matrix flow, interface debonding or matrix fracture. The failure is closely related to the number of fibre ends and thus to the parameters including fibre volume fraction, fibre length and fibre radius. Consequently, a relationship between composite failure strain and fibre volume fraction should exist. For this reason, an examination of fibre volume fraction was undertaken using TGA in an inert atmosphere. Figure 4 shows a typical TGA trace for the change in weight over temperature. With these results, and knowing the density of the carbon fibre and the density of the polymer (confirmed using density buoyancy method) the fibre volume fraction (FVF) could be calculated. The results for FVF are given in table 4. It was found that both polymer types exhibited similar values for FVF. As expected the FVF increased with fibre filament count. The 3k CF gave a FVF of approximately 5%, the 6k approximately 8% and the 12k approximately 15%. Therefore, the increase in strength and modulus observed in these trials are similar to the results reported previously where these properties increase with increasing FVF [9].

Figure 4. Typical TGA trace

Table 4. Fibre volume fraction results.

Sample	% Fibre volume fraction		Sample	% Fibre volume fraction
HDPE 3k	4.7		PP 3k	4.6
HDPE 6k	8.5		PP 6k	7.9
HDPE 12k	14.9		PP 12k	15.5
HDPE 6k US	7.7		PP 6k US	8.5

Figure 5. Typical micrograph of fracture surface.

The micrographs show good dispersion of the CF in the polymer matrix in all composite specimens. Figure 5 shows a typical fracture surface where it can be seen that the fibers are aligned preferentially along the flow direction. Brittle fracture of the matrix is observed in both HDPE and PP composites, consistent with the brittle nature of the tensile stress–strain curves and reduced elongation at break. It was also observed that most fibers are pulled out from the matrix with little or no fibre breakage. At his level of magnification however, no difference was observed between the sized and unsized fibres.

CONCLUSIONS

This paper has reported that waste carbon fibre reclaimed from the 3D weaving process can be easily melt compounded with commodity thermoplastics. The extruded strands can then be chopped into granules and injection moulded into components with fibres aligned preferentially along the flow direction and a fibre volume fraction of 15 % or greater.

The carbon fibre was found to be well distributed in the thermoplastic melt in all specimens tested. Experiments show that with increasing fibre volume fraction the Ultimate tensile strength can be increased by up to 77% in the case of HDPE and 25% with PP.

By increasing the fibre volume fraction, Young's modulus can be increased by approximately 1000% for both polymer types by the addition of approximately 15% fibre volume. It was determined however, that the composites are brittle with large reductions in elongation at break observed for all composites tested.

Further work is required to assess the importance of sizing. The removal of the sizing appears to reduce modulus values for both polymer types and give an improvement in UTS for HDPE but not PP. In both cases the removal of sizing improved the % elongation at break.

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